

Microwave-assisted one pot highly efficient synthesis of 1,3-benzothiazoles and 1,3-benzoxazole

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Abstract : Highly efficient and cost effective cyclocondensation of 2-aminothiophenols/2-aminophenols and carboxylic acids to give benzothiazoles/benzoxazoles has been reported under microwave irradiation condition using pyridine and triphenyl phosphite (TPP). The one pot methodology allowed shorter reaction times, easy isolation of the products and good to excellent yields. The method is practical and efficient for parallel synthesis of the important class of heterocyclic compounds.

Keywords : Benzothiazole, benzoxazole, triphenyl phosphite, pyridine, microwave.

Introduction

2-Substituted benzothiazoles and benzoxazoles are important class of heterocyclic compounds in pharmaceutical chemistry. They have wide range of biological and pharmaceutical properties such as antiviral¹, antifungal², antitumor³, anti-inflammatory⁴, antimicrobial⁵ and NSAID flunoxaprofen or inhibitors of CETP activity⁶. The two drugs, one in benzothiazole series e.g. riluzole (use to treat amyotrophic lateral sclerosis) and one in benzoxazole series e.g. flunoxaprofen (a chiral non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug) have shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Benzoxazole and benzothiazole drugs.

The currently used methodologies for the synthesis of 2-substituted benzothiazoles or 2-substituted benzoxazoles are the condensation reactions of *o*-aminobenzenethiol or *o*-aminophenol with substituted carboxylic acids⁷, aldehydes, alcohols⁸, acyl chlorides⁹, nitriles¹⁰ and by cy-

clization of thiobenzamides¹¹. Soraia *et al.*¹² synthesized benzothiazoles from carboxylic acids, tetrabutylammonium bromide (TBAB) and triphenyl phosphite (TPP). But most of the methodologies require long reaction time, use of corrosive acids like polyphosphoric acid¹³, use of costly ionic liquids, tedious work-up, formation of toxic side products and more cost-effective. Wen *et al.*¹⁴ synthesized 1,3-benzazoles (benzothiazoles, benzoxazoles and benzimidazoles) by using T₃P (in AcOEt)/DIPEA in microwave. Recently, Lin and coworkers have reported microwave-assisted one step synthesis of benzimidazoles by the reaction of benzene-1,2-diamine with benzoic acid in the presence of triphenyl phosphite (TPP) in pyridine under microwave irradiation at 220 °C¹⁵.

As per our knowledge, no benzothiazole and benzoxazole are reported using TPP in pyridine under microwave irradiation. We have checked different conditions and using modified condition (triphenyl phosphite, pyridine as reagent, under microwave irradiation at 150 °C) we have tried to evaluate the synthesis of benzothiazole and benzoxazole. We have not used pyridine as a solvent but only 2 equivalent. By this way we have tried to make our system more environmentally friendly, as well as,

easy to work up. Our method is very easy, cost-effective and tolerated broad range of substitutions.

Results and discussion

The general reaction for the synthesis of 2-substituted 1,3-benzothiazole and 2-substituted 1,3-benzoxazole is shown in Scheme 1. For the reactions we have used *o*-aminobenzenethiol or *o*-aminophenol with substituted carboxylic acids in the presence of TPP and base under microwave (MW) irradiation. We have started our model reaction with *o*-aminobenzenethiol and benzoic acid and irradiated the mixture using different conditions (Table 1).

Scheme 1. General scheme for the synthesis of benzothiazoles and benzoxazoles.

Table 1. Optimization of reaction condition

Entry	Base	Solvent	Temp.	Result (%) ^a
1	–	THF	rt	None
2	Pyridine	THF	rt	Trace
3	DMAP (2 eq)	–	rt	Trace
4	DMAP (2 eq)	–	100 °C	35.1
5	DMAP (2 eq)	–	MW, 150 °C	40.7
6	Pyridine (2 eq)	–	100 °C	58.3
7	Pyridine (2 eq)	–	MW, 150 °C	71
8	Pyridine (excess)	Pyridine	MW, 150 °C	71

^aIsolated yield.

It was observed that the pyridine as base and at 150 °C in MW irradiation has been given the best result and we have used the condition to make the substituted 2-substituted-1,3-benzothiazole which is shown in Table 2.

We have chosen different types of substituted acids, starting from un-substituted benzoic acid **2a** (entry 1) which

is given 71% yield. All the experimental results have summarized in Table 2 and the yield of the reaction are moderate to high. We have used electron donating as well as electron withdrawing groups. 4-Cyanobenzoic acid **2b** (entry 2) and 4-methoxybenzoic acid **2c** (entry 3) gave 57% and 55% yield respectively. So, it looks that our reaction condition is equally effective for both electron withdrawing and electron donating group. Alkyl substituted benzoic acid **2d** gave very high yield (92%, entry 4). The protocol is equally active with heteroaromatic (5 or 6 member ring) and fused heteroaromatic rings. Pyridine-2-carboxylic acid (nicotinic acid) **2e** and furan-2-carboxylic acid **2f** gave 2-substituted-1,3-benzothiazole **3e** and **3f** respectively with high yield (entries 5 and 6). In this regard our protocol is more effective than any other reported methods. The methodology is also effective with the fused aromatic acids and benzofuran-2-carboxylic acid **2g** on applying the same condition gave the product **3g** in 36% yield.

We have also implemented our methodology for the synthesis of benzoxazoles and found that our methodology is equally effective for the synthesis of 2-substituted-1,3-benzoxazoles. We have chosen different varieties of aromatic acids, starting from un-substituted benzoic acid **2a** (entry 1), pyridine-3-carboxylic acid (nicotinic acid) **2e** and furan-2-carboxylic acid **2f**. All the experimental results have been summarized in Table 3. The Table shows that the yields of the reaction are very high from 79% to 96%. All the synthesized compounds were well characterized by mass and NMR and compared with the reported value whenever available.

Experimental

General procedures : The ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ and DMSO-*d*₆ at 400 MHz. The chemical shifts are reported in ppm downfield to TMS (δ = 0) for ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR. LCMS spectra were obtained with Water acuity SQD 3100 mass detector. Melting points were recorded in open capillary and were uncorrected. Column chromatography was carried out on silica gel (100–200 mesh) purchased from

Table 2. Synthesis of benzothiazoles using TPP, pyridine in MW irradiation

Entry	Acid	Product	Yield (%) ^a
1	 2a	 3a	71
2	 2b	 3b	57
3	 2c	 3c	55
4	 2d	 3d	92
5	 2e	 3e	98
6	 2f	 3f	78
7	 2g	 3g	36

^aIsolated yield.

Spectrochem and TLC was carried out using aluminium sheets pre-coated with silica gel 60 F254 purchased from Merck. All the solvents and chemicals used were reagent grade procured from Spectrochem, Alfa Aesar and Finar.

General procedure for the synthesis of 2-substituted-1,3-benzothiazoles and benzoxazoles :

A mixture of *o*-aminobenzenethiol/*o*-aminophenol (1

mmol), carboxylic acid (1 mmol), anhydrous pyridine (2 mmol) and triphenyl phosphite (1 mmol) was irradiated for 30 min under microwave (max. setting power : 150 W and max. setting pressure : 17 bar) at 150 °C. The completion of the reaction was confirmed by TLC. Reaction was quenched with 10% sodium hydroxide solution and extracted with ethyl acetate. The organic layer was washed with brine solution, dried over Na₂SO₄ and con-

Scheme 2. Proposed reaction mechanism.

Table 3. Synthesis of 2-substituted-1,3-benzoxazoles using TPP, pyridine in MW irradiation

Entry	Acid	Product	Yield (%) ^a
1		83	
2		79	
3		96	
4		44.5	

^aIsolated yield.

centrated under reduced pressure. The crude residue was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, 10% EtOAc/hexane) to get respective benzothiazole.

The structures of the products were confirmed by NMR and liquid chromatography associated with mass spectroscopy.

Conclusions

We have reported an efficient and quick synthesis of 2-substituted-1,3-benzothiazole and 2-substituted-1,3-benzoxazole using TPP and pyridine in MW irradiation. Our protocol is very cost effective; we have used less costly aromatic acids instead of aldehydes, less costly reagents like PPA and pyridine (only 2 equivalents). Like other methods, we are not using any additional organic solvents or ionic liquids or any other reagents and the method is environmentally friendly. Our protocol is cover wide range of aromatic acids and suitable for rapidly synthesis of large number of compound library with low cost for biological studies in medicinal chemistry.

Characterization of synthesized compounds :

2-Phenylbenzo[d]thiazole (3a) :

¹H NMR : (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) : δ 7.39 (1H, t, *J* 7.6 Hz), 7.48–7.51 (4H, m), 7.91 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 8.07 (1H, s), 8.09–8.11 (2H, m); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 121.75, 123.41, 125.32, 126.44, 131.08, 133.83, 135.25, 154.35, 168.18; m.p. 216–220 °C; MS (*m/z*) : 212 (M⁺).

4-(Benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl)benzonitrile (3b) :

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) : δ 7.43–7.47 (1H, m), 7.53–7.56 (1H, m), 7.78–7.80 (2H, m), 7.95 (1H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 8.11 (1H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 8.20–8.23 (2H, m); ¹³C

NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 114.32, 118.41, 121.95, 123.98, 126.23, 126.98, 128.10, 132.92, 135.49, 137.68, 154.21, 165.48; m.p. 295–302 °C; MS (*m/z*) : 236.9 (M⁺).

2-(4-Propylphenyl)benzo[d]thiazole (3c) :

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) : δ 4.07 (3H, s), 7.05–7.09 (1H, m), 7.12–7.15 (1H, m), 7.35–7.39 (1H, m), 7.44–7.51 (2H, m), 7.93 (1H, d, *J* 7.6 Hz), 8.09 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 8.52–8.54 (1H, m); MS (*m/z*) : 242.04 (M⁺).

2-(4-Methylphenethyl)benzo[d]thiazole (3d) :

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) : δ 2.42 (3H, s), 3.15–3.19 (2H, m), 3.39–3.43 (2H, m), 7.10–7.17 (4H, m), 7.33–7.37 (1H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz), 7.44–7.47 (1H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz), 7.83 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 7.98 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 35.21, 36.21, 121.60, 122.67, 124.81, 126.00, 128.38, 129.34, 135.23, 136.00, 137.20, 153.31, 171.13; m.p. 258–266 °C; MS (*m/z*) : 254.0 (M⁺).

2-(Pyridin-3-yl)benzo[d]thiazole (3e) :

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) : δ 7.42–7.46 (2H, m), 7.51–7.55 (1H, m), 7.94 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 8.11 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 8.37–8.40 (1H, m), 8.71–8.73 (1H, m), 9.30 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 121.83, 123.62, 123.85, 125.80, 126.72, 129.82, 134.61, 135.11, 148.74, 151.70, 154.11, 164.65; m.p. 268–273 °C; MS (*m/z*) : 212.96 (M⁺).

2-(Furan-2-yl)benzo[d]thiazole (3f) :

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) : δ 6.59–6.61 (1H, m), 7.20 (1H, d, *J* 3.2 Hz), 7.38–7.40 (1H, m), 7.47–7.51 (1H, m), 7.61 (1H, s), 7.89 (1H, d, *J* 7.6 Hz), 8.05 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 111.57, 112.68, 121.71, 123.28, 125.34, 126.62, 144.85; m.p. 220–225 °C; MS (*m/z*) : 201.94 (M⁺).

2-(Benzofuran-2-yl)benzo[d]thiazole (3g) :

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) : δ 7.29–7.33 (1H, m), 7.40–7.45 (2H, m), 7.51–7.54 (2H, m), 7.62 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 7.69 (1H, d, *J* 7.6 Hz), 7.95 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 8.13 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz); m.p. 315–320 °C; MS (*m/z*) : 251.8 (M⁺).

2-Phenylbenzo[d]oxazole (6a) :

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) : δ 7.34–7.37 (2H, m), 7.52–7.54 (3H, m), 7.58–7.60 (1H, m), 7.76–7.79 (1H, m), 8.25–8.28 (2H, m); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : 110.70, 120.13, 124.68, 125.21, 127.27, 127.73, 129.02, 131.62, 142.22, 150.87, 163.15; m.p. 160–165 °C.

2-(Pyridin-3-yl)benzo[d]oxazole (6b) :

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) : δ 7.37–7.42 (2H, m), 7.46–7.49 (1H, m), 7.61–7.63 (1H, m), 7.79–7.81 (1H, m), 7.52 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 8.77 (1H, s), 9.48 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : 110.90, 120.44, 123.80, 125.06, 125.85, 134.84, 141.95, 148.93, 150.92, 152.18, 160.84; m.p. 225–230 °C; MS (*m/z*) : 197.14 (M⁺).

2-(Furan-2-yl)benzo[d]oxazole (6c) :

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) : δ 6.62–6.63 (1H, m), 7.28–7.31 (1H, m), 7.35–7.37 (2H, m), 7.55–7.58 (1H, m), 7.67 (1H, s), 7.75–7.77 (1H, m); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : 110.68, 112.38, 114.40, 115.59, 120.25, 124.96, 125.40, 141.73, 142.71, 145.85, 150.24, 155.41; m.p. 168–175 °C.

2-(2-Methoxyphenyl)benzo[d]oxazole (6d) :

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) : δ 4.05 (3H, s), 7.09–7.12 (1H, m), 7.32–7.37 (1H, m), 7.49–7.53 (1H, m), 7.58–7.60 (1H, m), 7.81–7.83 (1H, m), 8.13–8.15 (1H, m); m.p. 205–210 °C; MS (*m/z*) : 226.20 (M⁺).

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